

Transforming A Maintenance Ground Station

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Abstract—Diagnostics^{1,2} information from the V-22 Osprey aircraft is processed using the Aircraft Maintenance Event Ground Station (AMEGS). Afterward, this information is debriefed with the aircrew and maintainers to determine if any gripes should be written to repair, service, or inspect the aircraft. Early in development, the downloaded maintenance data was rarely used because of numerous Built-In-Test (BIT) false alarms, and AMEGS was not integrated with the Naval Aviation Logistics Command Management Information System Optimized Organization Maintenance Activity (NALCOMIS-OOMA). Today, AMEGS is an integral part of the V-22's Automated Maintenance Environment (AME) providing the capability to generate work orders from the aircraft's BIT and Vibration, Structural Life and Engine Diagnostics (VSLED). Furthermore, AMEGS has taken the first step towards establishing a link to the Interactive Electronic Technical Manual (IETM) by displaying a cross-reference from a Fault ID to IETM code so the maintainer has a starting point to begin troubleshooting once a work order is generated. This paper discusses how the AMEGS displays were transformed from an engineering tool into a user-friendly format for maintenance and how AMEGS became an instrumental aspect of the V-22's AME in the fleet.

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1. INTRODUCTION

After a mission, the aircrew will bring the Data Transfer Module (DTM) containing the downloaded maintenance data into maintenance control. Maintenance personnel will download the aircraft's maintenance and VSLED data into

AMEGS. Maintenance control and the various shops will debrief BIT indications with the pilots using the different AMEGS reports. If the aircrew observed an anomaly and a code also set on that system, maintenance personnel will generate a work order through AMEGS into NALCOMIS-OOMA. Several of the data elements in AMEGS will also be recorded onto the work order to assist the various levels of maintenance (i.e., organizational, intermediate, and depot) with repairing the equipment.

The Blue Ribbon Panel report of April 2001 was instrumental in driving the transformation of the V-22 program to embrace the AME concept. AMEGS improvements resulted from implementing corrective actions for the following recommendations by the Blue Ribbon Panel:

- Fix the individual deficiencies associated with AMEGS, IETM, and NALCOMIS (Optimized). After each system demonstrates adequate reliability, integrate these three systems as soon as possible.
- In the short term, expedite software cross-references for AMEGS and IETMs.
- Expedite the plan to reduce the V-22 false-alarm rate in both the aircraft and ground systems, with priority on aircraft software.

2. AMEGS SYSTEM DESCRIPTION

AMEGS has been developed to support the on-condition maintenance concept of the V-22 Osprey aircraft. AMEGS assists the functions of a maintenance manager, administrator, and record keeper and is used for the purposes of examining downloaded maintenance data and creating reports, reference [1].

Maintenance Download Function

As shown in figure 1, the DTM is the physical medium used to transfer aircraft diagnostics data to the AMEGS workstation. Downloading of this data is accomplished using the AMEGS Program Loader screen as shown in figure 2. Current status of the diagnostics information is displayed in the window.

¹ "U.S. Government work not protected by U.S. copyright." For U.S. Government employees only.

² IEEEAC paper #1086, Version 5, Updated November 16, 2004

Figure 1. Data Transfer Module

Figure 2. Program Loader Screen

Process VSLED Files

VSLED data is processed via the Performance Trend Model Program (PTMP) and the Dynamic Component Monitoring Program (DCMP). PTMP calculates the engine performance and vibration trend data. A typical display of the engine performance trend data is depicted in figure 3. DCMP monitors many aircraft components such as bearings, rotors, etc. and alerts the user of any out of tolerance readings. A component vibration trend chart is illustrated in figure 4.

Maintenance Download Summary

Figure 5 shows the maintenance download summary window where a majority of the aircraft indications are presented to the aircrew and maintainers. Icons at the top of the window provide quick, easy sorting of the information into reports for interpretation and correlation with aircrew observed anomalies. On the right side of the display, the Flight Tree lists all the aircraft in the squadron as well as visiting aircraft. The ten most recent downloads are displayed for each aircraft. All downloads for the aircraft are viewable by clicking on "More". A listing of the different types of indications and their color-coding is

presented in table I. The color coding is consistent with what the aircrew observes in the cockpit.

Table I

List of Aircraft Indications And Their Color Coding in AMEGS

Indication	Color
Warning	Red
Caution	Yellow
Advisory (WCA)	White
Weapons Replaceable Assembly (WRA)	Green
Exceedance (EXC)	Blue
Consumable/Maintenance Indication (C/MI)	Magenta
System Discrete	Light Blue

Maintenance Summary Detail Window

After selecting a WCA, WRA, EXC, or C/MI in the maintenance summary window, additional information is presented in the maintenance summary detail window. This additional information includes aircraft state data, such as, nacelle angle, altitude, outside air temperature, airspeed, and other operating parameters. In addition, fault data that is reported over the aircraft's MIL-STD-1553B data bus is also shown so it can be analyzed by engineering.

VSLED Download Summary

Figure 6 shows the VSLED download summary, which presents various types of status and maintenance indications related to engine vibration and performance and selected aircraft component vibration data.

Work Orders

Figure 7 depicts the information from a WRA indication that is being sent to NALCOMIS-OOMA to be recoded into a work order. Work orders can be generated for both maintenance and VSLED indications; however they are selectively generated by the operator and are not automatically created during each download.

3. TRANSITION TO AME

Background

After the Blue Ribbon Report, the overall approach for utilizing AMEGS, NALCOMIS-OOMA, and IETM was re-evaluated. From this review, a number of changes were made to move towards an integrated set of products.

Figure 3. AMEGS Engine Performance Plot

Figure 4. AMEGS Component Vibration Trend Chart

Figure 5. AMEGS Maintenance Download Summary Window

Figure 6. AMEGS VSLED Summary Window

Download Summary Version 4.1: NALCOMIS System: Unfiltered: ALL Types: Work Order Submission Form

File View Window Options Help

ALL WRA CMI

AIRCRAFT ID: 164940 Flight: 29/10/03

AIRCRAFT ID: 164940 Submit Date: 17/11/03 Submit Time: 11:04:46

Description: *DSIU - DSIU
S/R: S
BIT Results: F(P)
IETM S/S/S: 6326AJ
Mmode: OFF
Date: 29/10/03
Time: 19:07:50

1553 Data: 1/3300 2/0000 3/2720 4/27C0 5/4120 6/0000 7/0000 8/0000
9/0005 10/0000 11/0000 12/0000 13/0000 14/0000 15/0000 16/0000
17/0000 18/0000 19/0000 20/0000 21/0000 22/0000 23/0000 24/0000
25/0000 26/0000 27/0000 28/0000 29/0000 30/0000 31/0000 32/0000

1553 Translations: No Fault Data Translation

Initiated By: [] Fault Type: WRA
When Discovered: A: Before Flight - Abort - Aircrew Fault ID: 56AD

Aircraft Status: Up Down

Summary Details: Log Maint Detail

Maintenance Data: AIRCRAFT
MAINTENANCE WRA FAULT - DE
AIRCRAFT ID: 164940 Dow:
Fault ID:
WO/JCN: No

Flight Tree: resident
164939
164940
29/10/03 - 19:29:42
MAINT
VSLED
29/10/03 - 18:49:06
24/10/03 - 18:33:30
24/10/03 - 14:36:16
23/10/03 - 17:01:24
23/10/03 - 14:13:28
22/10/03 - 17:42:50
22/10/03 - 16:26:12
22/10/03 - 13:32:30
21/10/03 - 16:01:18
More
164941
164942
165434
165435
165438
165442
165443
165444
165837
165848
165941
visiting

Submit Print Cancel

Unfiltered | All Types | Descending -- Latest flight first | All Flights Displayed

Figure 7. AMEGS Work Order

Determining The Users Needs

As part of the re-evaluation process, coordination meetings were held with the V-22 Maintainer Integrated Product Team to determine how the work centers in the maintenance department would use AMEGS. As a result, the displays could be designed to support their needs. The different maintenance shops required the following functions:

- a. Maintenance control: debrief aircrew and generate work orders.
- b. Maintenance shops: troubleshooting, servicing, and inspections.
- c. Quality assurance: BIT trending and VSLED analysis.

Interpreting And Presenting The Data

AMEGS can display up to 800 lines in the maintenance download summary window, which is dictated by the aircraft's design. A multitude of different types of information are contained in these 800 lines; (1) normal status information (WCA indications), (2) failures of equipment (WRA indications), (3) servicing (C/MI indications), (4) overstress conditions (EXC indications), and (5) system discrete (i.e., weight-off-wheels, engine start, etc.). Some indications require maintenance actions and some would not. Therefore, reports based upon a maintenance requirement were needed to sort the data quickly into a format for easy interpretation and led to the three report types below:

- a. WRA report – identifies the equipment that has set failed during the mission.
- b. C/MI report– identifies the systems that require servicing.
- c. EXC report– identifies the systems that have experienced an overstress condition and requires an inspection or replacement of parts.

Modifying the Displays

Originally, the AMEGS maintenance download and VSLED summary windows had small icons at the top that were used to perform the various operations in AMEGS, figure 8. Pull-down windows were also provided to sort and filter the indications in a multitude of ways. These icons and pull-down windows were okay for performing engineering analyses; however, they were not well suited for maintenance operations.

Large pushbuttons replaced the small icons and pull-downs at the top of the maintenance and VSLED summary windows. These pushbuttons were labeled with the report name that corresponds to the type of indications that need to be reviewed and interpreted. Furthermore, the WORK ORDER and PRINT functions were also assigned pushbuttons since these features are regularly used. The Flight Tree was better organized using the “More” feature so this window was not cluttered with past AMEGS downloads displaying only the most recent 10 files.

4. LESSONS LEARNED

The following lessons learned are recommended for future programs.

Categorizing Indications

During aircraft development, various diagnostics information needs to be categorized and presented to the aircrew and maintainers in a manner that supports the maintenance concept of the aircraft and the business model for maintenance operations. Basic types of maintenance indications are: (1) failures, (2) servicing/maintenance, and (3) overstress.

(1) Failures are reported by the equipment's internal BIT, and the severity of the failure should be identified on the cockpit displays for aircrew situational awareness.

(2) Servicing/maintenance indications should comprise the following types of conditions:

- a. Low fluid level.
- b. Over-filled fluid level.
- c. Impending filter bypass.
- d. Actual filter bypass.
- e. Clogged barrier filters.
- f. Software constants need to be loaded via software.
- g. Maintenance and VSLED data are full and require downloading before over-writing occurs.
- h. Chip/debris detected in gearbox.
- i. Fire protection system needs servicing.
- j. Low nitrogen pressure.
- k. Single communication multiplex bus failure indications.
- l. Battery low power (requires charge).

(3) Overstress indications should comprise the following types of conditions:

- a. Over temperature exposure.
- b. High vibration levels.
- c. Electrical power out of tolerance.
- d. Over speed.
- e. Over torque.

Engineering information that just identifies current status of equipment operation should not be presented along with maintenance related indications. These indications should only be viewable in a special report that is not normally used for maintenance operations.

Supporting Maintenance Operations

Figure 9 identifies the typical maintenance operations that a ground station would be required to assist the Navy/Marine maintainer. Obviously, the aircraft has to be

Figure 8. Original AMEGS Maintenance Download Summary Window

- Ground station presents aircraft info to support OPNAV 4790 maintenance operations

- Functionality to support maintenance operations

Figure 9. Typical Maintenance Operations That a Ground Station Needs to Support

equipped with the required BIT and sensors along with the software to record this information for processing by the ground station. The following features will greatly enhance the ground station's role in any aircraft's AME:

(1) Generate Work Orders in NALCOMIS-OOMA: Integrate the ground station with NALCOMIS-OOMA so that sufficient diagnostics information can be recorded onto the work orders to assist the various levels of maintenance (i.e., organizational, intermediate, and depot) with repairing the equipment.

(2) Pilot Debrief Mode: During pilot debrief, the aircrew has the option to enter observed anomalies which can be used to ascertain whether the system is operating normally under environmental conditions which can cause a system to appear as though it has failed, reference [2]. For example, radar imagery may contain anomalies when flying over choppy oceans while the RADAR is looking down. Providing a picture of common anomalies that are not failures would enhance this feature. Pilot debrief mode will prevent unnecessary maintenance and will reduce false removals.

(3) Highlight Known False Alarms: Identify known BIT false alarms in a manner easily viewable from other codes, and provide a descriptive narrative explaining the conditions when this code is considered a false alarm and the expected corrective action, if known. This function will minimize unnecessary maintenance and will reduce false removals.

(4) Trending: Provide the capability to count and display the number of occurrences codes set on all the squadron's aircraft with special emphasis on the last 10 flights. In addition, highlight codes as known false alarms or true detections based upon reliability/maintainability analyses. This function will improve mission capability rates and overall squadron readiness, as cited in reference [3]:

- a. Averaging 68 flight-hours and 44 sorties more per month than all the squadrons.
- b. Combat ready six months prior to deployment date, 33% faster than scheduled.

(5) Detailed Subsystem BIT Reports: Provide reports for each subsystem that identifies the failed function inside the WRA along with mode changes. Aircraft operating conditions should be recorded with this information to support root cause analysis of false alarms. This feature will assist maintainers with troubleshooting isolation ambiguities. For example, if a power supply failed first in the controlling WRA and the other two WRAs in the subsystem also were declared failed afterward, a detailed subsystem report would identify the power supply failure causing the other two ambiguous failure indications.

(6) Aircraft Software Configuration: A listing of all software on-board the aircraft needs to be recorded on each flight.

Oil Servicing Levels

Oil levels for engines and gearboxes should be presented as a special report on the ground station especially on aircraft with blade fold/wing stow for shipboard operations. These levels should be recorded at engine shutdown while the oil levels are still valid for reading. The levels should be presented in ounces, which is compatible with oil-servicing units. Furthermore, ensure IETM contains procedures to use the oil servicing levels presented on the ground station.

Exporting Data

Data in the different reports should be exported into a format that is easily imported into databases normally used by government and industry team members.

Integration With NALCOMIS-OOMA

(1) When generating a work order, the current date and time should be recorded vice the date and time that the aircraft indication occurred. Incorrect date and time information transferred to the maintenance work order form will adversely degrade mission readiness performance of the weapon system.

(2) Only show one IETM troubleshooting task for each indication on the ground station so the presentation and output reports are not highly cluttered.

(3) When generating a work order, the default for the When Discovered code should be a "blank" status requiring operator selection of the correct code. Furthermore, the severity of the When Discovered code should coincide with the aircraft status as "Up" or "Down". In addition, a verification window should also be added for When Discovered codes "A" (Before Flight – Abort – Aircrew) and "C" (In Flight – Abort – Aircrew) so the operator must acknowledge that this gripe actually caused an abort. This feature will minimize human error from artificially inflating the number of aircraft aborts, which adversely degrades reliability performance of the weapon system.

Sorting and Filtering Data

(1) Sorting and filtering functions need to be reset to a standard configuration when the ground station is first started or when new data is downloaded into the system. This will minimize incorrect interpretation of the aircraft indications.

(2) Ensure the displays and output reports clearly identify that the information has been sorted in a non-standard manner so it is not incorrectly interpreted.

5. CONCLUSIONS

Improving AMEGS for the maintainer has truly been a completely integrated effort by everyone on the V-22 Osprey team. Sustainment program managers, fleet support team engineers, maintainers, and diagnostics professionals from the Marine Corps, Navy, Air Force, Bell-Boeing, Rolls-Royce, and Raytheon team have all worked together to transform AMEGS. AMEGS has become an instrumental part of the Osprey's automated maintenance environment. There still remains the challenge of "Fixing BIT" to eliminate false alarms, and this issue is being aggressively worked.

REFERENCES

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